
MARGIN PLAY: A MULTI-AGENT SYSTEM FOR PUBLIC POLICY ANALYSIS IN THE BRAZILIAN EQUATORIAL MARGIN

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ABSTRACT

The Brazilian Equatorial Margin (BEM) constitutes the next frontier of offshore oil exploration in Brazil, with operations expected to begin in 2026 in the Foz do Amazonas basin. The BEM assets are fiscally and territorially linked, primarily, to the state of Maranhão, currently the state with the lowest Human Development Index in the Federation (HDI 0.676, IBGE 2022). This gives rise to the central public policy question of this work: to what extent and under what conditions does oil exploration in the BEM generate net positive externalities for the state of Maranhão? The problem is intrinsically multi-agent: the Federal Government seeks tax revenue and energy security; the state seeks regional welfare under constitutional royalty earmarking; the operator maximizes profit subject to operational risk; the ANP and IBAMA represent conflicting institutional mandates; and Amazonian communities assign greater weight to territorial and environmental vectors than to monetary income. We present Margin Play, a Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning (MARL) system that simulates these tensions under Brazilian empirical calibration (Law 9.478/97, Law 12.858/2013, Petrobras Form 20-F, TCU 2.936/2021, MMA NDC 2024, CPT/INCRA/CIMI 2024) and grounded in classical economic literature (Aschauer–Munnell, Cobb–Douglas, CRRA, Atkinson, van der Ploeg). The system implements six agents under the CTDE paradigm (Centralized Training, Decentralized Execution) trained with BRO-MARL. The results, obtained from 60,000 episodes distributed across six scenarios (three macroeconomic baselines, two policy counterfactuals and one structural transformative regime designated MA-Próspero), indicate that the answer to the central question is conditional on the adopted institutional regime: under the reference baseline, the welfare gain is marginal ($W_{\text{aval}} \approx 1.68$), whereas the MA-Próspero parametric configuration yields $\Delta W = +17.5\%$ and $\Delta R_{\text{com}} = +21.3\%$, simultaneously with an environmental liability below the reference ($E_{\text{amb}} = 0.048$ vs. 0.076). It is concluded that the fundamental problem does not consist in a trade-off between production and welfare, but in the choice of the public policy regime linked to exploration.

Keywords Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning · Brazilian Equatorial Margin · Maranhão · Public Policy · Offshore Oil · Cobb–Douglas · Atkinson · CTDE · BRO · royalties

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1 Introduction

1.1 Context and Motivation

The Brazilian Equatorial Margin (BEM) is a geological complex extending from Amapá to Rio Grande do Norte, encompassing five offshore sedimentary basins (Foz do Amazonas, Pará-Maranhão, Barreirinhas, Ceará and Potiguar), as illustrated in fig. 1. Estimates of undiscovered potential from the National Petroleum, Natural Gas and Biofuels Agency (ANP) suggest potential reserves of 10 to 30 billion barrels of oil equivalent [1]. It is noteworthy that the Barreirinhas basin — whose fiscal-territorial affiliation also falls on the state of Maranhão — presents distinct techno-economic optimization challenges, notably in carbonate matrix stimulation processes, whose viability depends on the integration of reactive flow simulations with Net Present Value (NPV) metrics, directly influencing the cost and risk structures assumed by operators [1].

Figure 1: Map of the Brazilian Equatorial Margin (BEM) with the five offshore sedimentary basins (Foz do Amazonas, Pará-Maranhão, Barreirinhas, Ceará and Potiguar) and the state of Maranhão highlighted as the primary fiscal-territorial affiliate. *The designations employed and the presentation of material in this map do not imply the expression of any opinion on the part of the authors concerning the legal status of any country, territory, city or area.*

The region became the focus of regulatory tension between 2023 and 2025 with the FZA-M-59 case: Petrobras applied for a drilling licence in the Foz do Amazonas basin; the Brazilian Institute of Environment and Renewable Natural Resources (IBAMA) denied the licence [2] due to deficiencies in the emergency plan; the Ministry of Environment (MMA), initially aligned with IBAMA, subsequently positioned itself in favour of re-analysis [3]. The conflict illustrates the complexity of the multi-agent problem: a single project involves fiscal interests (Federal Government), constitutional equity interests (state), operational interests (Petrobras), procedural-environmental interests (IBAMA), technical-regulatory interests (ANP) and socio-territorial interests (Amazonian communities), under legal constraints ranging from the Federal Constitution of 1988 [4] to specific resolutions such as ANP Resolution 882/2022 [5].

Following the granting of the drilling licence for the Morphi FZA-M-59 well in October 2025, Petrobras announced an investment of approximately US\$ 3 billion for the drilling of 16 wells in the BEM between 2025 and 2029, con-

solidating the transition from geological promise to operational reality. This development validates the urgency of the analytical question addressed in this study.

The central question of this work can be stated as: to what extent and under what conditions does oil exploration in the BEM generate net positive externalities for the state of Maranhão? Maranhão is the state with primary fiscal-territorial affiliation to the Foz do Amazonas and Pará-Maranhão basins, and the one with the lowest HDI in the federation (0.676, IBGE 2022). The resource curse literature [6, 7] indicates that the influx of oil revenues produces ambiguous effects: positive via royalties, FUNDEB and GDP; negative via Dutch disease, institutional capture and intensification of territorial conflicts. The question is not purely theoretical: in 2024 the state recorded 363 land conflicts (1st place nationally, CPT [8]) and 49 cases of violence against indigenous peoples (CIMI [9]). Oil exploration in the BEM will take place within this pre-existing socio-territorial context.

Moreover, Hodler, Lechner and Raschky (2023) [10], applying a causal forest estimator to data from 3,800 sub-Saharan African districts, empirically confirmed that stronger institutions amplify the positive effect of mining activities on economic development and attenuate their negative effect on conflicts — providing causal machine learning validation for the institutional conditionality that is the central premise of this work.

Public policy analysis for this scenario requires analytical tools with four simultaneous properties: mandate heterogeneity, physical-economic coupling, calibration with national data, and robust counterfactual capacity [11–15].

1.2 Objectives and Contributions

Margin Play is proposed as a computational instrument for public policy analysis, and its contributions are organised along five dimensions. The first is a six-agent multi-agent architecture calibrated with Brazilian primary sources, including updated territorial calibration (H-TERR-2) based on CPT/INCRA/CIMI 2024 data (section 3). The second consists of reward functions with heterogeneous functional forms (CRRA, log-Aschauer, Atkinson, Cobb–Douglas, Hubbert) and R_{gov} with decomposition of Net Current Revenue into five components endogenously derived from Brazilian fiscal legislation. The third is the application of the BRO algorithm [16] under the CTDE paradigm [17], with distributional critic TQC (Truncated Quantile Critics) [18]. The fourth is the counterfactual analysis across six scenarios (section 4): three macroeconomic baselines, two policy counterfactuals and one structural transformative regime (MA-Próspero), totalling 60,000 episodes. The fifth is the characterisation of the MA-Próspero regime — a parametric configuration of six simultaneous structural interventions that, at equilibrium, yields $\Delta W = +17.5\%$ accompanied by an environmental liability below the reference.

2 Methodological Rationale

2.1 MARL as a Public Policy Analysis Tool

Traditional public policy analysis, anchored in Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) models or reduced-form econometric estimations, presents important limitations for the BEM case. CGE models assume, by construction, representative agents with homogeneous utility functions — a premise incompatible with the mandate heterogeneity among ANP, IBAMA and MMA [19]. Reduced-form econometric models are essentially retrospective and lose validity when applied to states not yet realised, such as the BEM’s full-production regime [11].

Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning (MARL) simultaneously overcomes these limitations: it admits agents with arbitrary objective functions, allows the learning of approximate Nash equilibria through repeated interaction [17], and the evaluation of trade-offs is performed directly via Monte Carlo sampling.

Margin Play’s positioning in the literature requires explicit differentiation. The AI Economist [20] established a two-level MARL framework for fiscal policy design. Margin Play extends this paradigm in three directions: (i) from two hierarchical levels to six institutionally heterogeneous agents, each with distinct and legally grounded objective functions; (ii) from a generic economy to a specific subnational fiscal-territorial context, calibrated with Brazilian primary data; and (iii) from symmetric mandates to structurally conflicting mandates — the IBAMA reward function is fundamentally opposed to that of the operator.

In the petroleum domain, Radovic et al. [21] employed deep MARL (A2C + PPO) to reveal robust macro strategies of international oil companies across 408 energy transition scenarios. Margin Play is complementary: where Radovic et al. [21] examine strategies of competing corporations, Margin Play examines equilibrium dynamics from the perspective of the institutional system surrounding the operator. In the domain of computationally calibrated simulation for Brazil, PolicySpace2 [22] constitutes the most relevant national precedent, which Margin Play advances by replacing fixed behavioural rules with strategic learning.

2.2 Centralized Training and Decentralized Execution (CTDE)

The CTDE paradigm [17] is particularly appropriate for the problem considered here. During centralised training, each critic observes the global system state, which mitigates the non-stationarity typical of purely decentralised MARL regimes. During execution, each actor decides based exclusively on its own local observation, reproducing the Brazilian institutional reality.

Margin Play implements CTDE with BRO-MARL, a combination that provides: (a) centralised critic access to the global state during training; (b) distributional TQC critics with 25 quantile atoms, addressing high-variance return regimes; and (c) six structurally heterogeneous actor networks, each with reward functions specific to its institutional mandate.

2.3 Brazilian Empirical Calibration

Margin Play is designed as an analytical tool for the specific Brazilian case, not for a generic oil-producing country. The mandatory earmarking of royalties to health and education, in the proportion of 75%/25%, is treated as a hard constraint of the physical model, as stipulated by Law 12.858/2013 [15], and not as an agent decision. The Federal Government’s share of offshore royalties is parametrised at approximately 22%, estimated from the fiscal regime in force under Law 9.478/1997 [23], maintained in force since March 2013 by an injunction granted in ADI 4917 MC/DF [24]. The operator’s lifting cost is calibrated from Petrobras Form 20-F 2024 [13], not from OPEC averages. The zonal weights of the Community agent’s reward function reflect Brazilian Amazonian ethnography, as per Escobar [25], Almeida [26], CIMI [9] and CPT [8].

3 Methodology

3.1 System Overview

?? presents the architecture of Margin Play. The fundamental cycle chains five steps: each of the six agents observes the global state s_t and produces an action a_t^i ; the combined actions $\mathbf{a}_t = (a_t^1, \dots, a_t^6)$ feed the physical-economic module; the state evolves from s_t to s_{t+1} via transition equations (Hubbert, Solow, Cobb–Douglas, environmental liability dynamics); each agent receives a specific reward r_t^i and stores the tuple in the replay buffer; and BRO-MARL training updates actors and critics under the CTDE paradigm.

Figure 2: System architecture of the Margin Play framework under the CTDE paradigm. Six institutional agents interact with the physical-economic environment. During centralized training, critics observe the full global state s_t ; during execution, each actor conditions its policy strictly on its local observation space.

3.2 World State and Operational Sequence

The state s_t contains physical, economic and institutional variables (table 1). The zonal variables K_{pub} , K_{hum} , $K_{\text{saúde}}$, K_{priv} , C_{inst} and N are 4-dimensional vectors, with one entry per mesoregion of Maranhão according to the IBGE classification.

Table 1: World state variables s_t .

Variable	Type	Description
P_{eff}	scalar	Effective production (Mbbls/d)
R	scalar	Remaining reserves (Gbbl)
$price$	scalar	Brent price (USD/bbl)
E_{amb}	scalar $\in [0, 1]$	Environmental liability
K_{pub}	4D vector	Public capital by zone
K_{hum}	4D vector	Human capital (education) by zone
$K_{\text{saúde}}$	4D vector	Health capital by zone
K_{priv}	4D vector	Private capital by zone
C_{inst}	4D vector $\in [0, 1]$	Institutional capital
N	4D vector	Population by zone (thousands)
ICMS, FPE, FUNDEB	scalars	State revenues (R\$ bn)
GDP_{state}	scalar	State GDP (R\$ bn)
W	scalar	Regional aggregate welfare

Figure 3 details the operational sequence of a complete episode, organised in three stages. In the input stage (step 1), the episode is initialised by the specification of a scenario, a random seed and the target state of Maranhão. In the initialisation stage (step 2), the state s_0 is loaded with the initial conditions of the four mesoregions — capital stocks, reserves, Brent price and initial environmental liability.

Figure 3: Operational sequence of a Margin Play episode. Input stage (steps 1–2), 15-step biennial time loop (steps 3–8) and post-episode with BRO-MARL update (step 9, suppressed in inference mode).

The time loop (steps 3–8) constitutes the core of the episode and repeats 15 biennial iterations, totalling a 30-year horizon. In step 3, each agent observes exclusively the fraction of the global state accessible under its mandate, in accordance with the decentralised execution of CTDE: the State Government observes capital stocks, sovereign fund, Gini index and ICMS/FPE revenues; the Operator observes reserves, price, environmental liability and inspection intensity; the ANP observes production, royalties, operational safety and local content; IBAMA observes environmental liability, community mobilisation and accountability metrics; the Community observes income, environmental quality, employment and human capital; the Federal Government observes national production, total royalties, environmental liability and price. In step 4, each agent produces its action from the neural network output, clipped to the valid range of each dimension. Step 5 reserves an optional human intervention point; in standard training and inference mode, it is ignored. In step 6, the world evolves two years through the physical-economic transition equations. In step 7, each agent receives its individual reward r_t^i and the tuple is stored in the replay buffer. Step 8 records the state in the visualisation panel (observer mode) or in the replay memory (training mode); upon reaching step 14, the episode ends. In the post-episode stage (step 9), in training mode, BRO-MARL samples 256 transitions and updates the six actors and the six distributional TQC critics; in inference mode, this step is suppressed.

3.3 Physical-Economic Model

3.3.1 Oil Production

Effective oil production is modelled by the asymmetric Hubbert curve [27, 28], a classical parametrisation to represent the temporal trajectory of fields with ramp-up, peak and progressive decline phases:

$$P_t^{\text{ef}} = P_{\text{max}}^{\text{ef}} \cdot e^{a(t/t_{\text{peak}}-1)} \cdot (t/t_{\text{peak}}) \cdot \alpha_{\text{inv}} \cdot \mathbf{1}_{R_t > 0}. \quad (1)$$

Here $P_{\text{max}}^{\text{ef}}$ denotes the maximum effective production (in Mbbls/d), t_{peak} the peak instant and a the asymmetry coefficient. The adoption of the asymmetric form, rather than the classical symmetric Hubbert, reflects the empirical observation that modern fields tend to exhibit faster decline than ascent, due to secondary and tertiary recovery technologies. The multiplication by $\alpha_{\text{inv}} \in [0, 1]$ couples the curve to the operator’s investment action; the indicator $\mathbf{1}_{R_t > 0}$ ensures that production ceases exactly when reserves are exhausted.

The maximum effective capacity results from the multiplicative composition of two regulatory levers: $P_{\text{max}}^{\text{ef}} = P_{\text{max}} \cdot \kappa_{\text{auction}} \cdot \kappa_{\text{approv}}$, where $\kappa_{\text{auction}} \in [1; 1.2]$ is determined by the offshore block licensing pace controlled by the Federal Government and captures the speed at which new blocks are auctioned in ANP rounds. The factor $\kappa_{\text{approv}} \in [0.8; 1.2]$ is determined by the ANP’s speed of approval of Development Plans and explicitly models the regulatory bottleneck of Development Plan approval, whose observed average lag in the BEM is of the order of 18 months, according to a TCU operational audit [29].

3.3.2 Environmental Liability Dynamics

The temporal trajectory of environmental liability E_{amb} is described by a balance equation with four terms, each representing a distinct physical-economic mechanism:

$$\frac{\Delta E_{\text{amb}}}{\Delta t} = \alpha_{\text{base}} P + \alpha_{\text{prod}}^{\text{ef}} P(1 - \varphi) - \theta_{\text{rem}} I_{\text{amb}} E_{\text{amb}} - \gamma_{\text{nat}} E_{\text{amb}}. \quad (2)$$

The term $\alpha_{\text{base}} P$ represents the irreducible environmental impact associated with production — liabilities that persist even under perfect inspection: water-cut, discarded drilling fluids, fugitive emissions.² The term $\alpha_{\text{prod}}^{\text{ef}} P(1 - \varphi)$ represents the avoidable impact, linearly attenuated by the local environmental inspection intensity $\varphi \in [0, 1]$; additionally, $\alpha_{\text{prod}}^{\text{ef}} = \alpha_{\text{prod}} \cdot (1 - 0.4 \cdot \text{fed_env_insp})$ incorporates the influence of the federal environmental inspection budget (IBAMA/ICMBio, per the 2024–2027 PPA), establishing a direct channel between the Federal Government’s environmental inspection action and environmental dynamics. The term $-\theta_{\text{rem}} I_{\text{amb}} E_{\text{amb}}$ represents active remediation proportional to the existing liability, encoding the principle that there is no remediation where there is no liability. Finally, $-\gamma_{\text{nat}} E_{\text{amb}}$ represents natural decay through abiotic processes.

3.3.3 Capital Stocks

The five capital stocks relevant to regional welfare follow the Solow accumulation structure, combined with the Aschauer–Munnell foundation for public capital:

$$K_{i,t+1} = (1 - \delta_i) K_{i,t} + \eta_i \cdot I_{i,t}, \quad (3)$$

²Fugitive emissions are quantified in accordance with the 2019 Refinement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines, Volume 2, Chapter 4; supplementary reference: CONAMA Resolution 462/2014.

where δ_i is the annual depreciation rate of stock i and η_i is the investment-to-installed-capital conversion efficiency. Table 2 reports the calibrated values, all anchored in established academic sources. The heterogeneity among stocks is methodologically significant: K_{pub} depreciates at 4% per year with an elasticity of 0.39 in GDP, reflecting the centrality of public capital in middle-income economies [12, 30]; K_{hum} exhibits lower depreciation (2%) consistent with Lucas’s hypothesis [31] of increasing returns to knowledge; $K_{\text{saúde}}$ depreciates at 5% following Grossman [32]; and K_{priv} at 7%, standard Cobb–Douglas calibration [33].

Table 2: Capital stock calibration.

Stock	δ (p.a.)	GDP Elast.	Source
K_{pub}	4%	$\beta \approx 0.39$	Aschauer [12], Munnell [30]
K_{hum}	2%	$\gamma \approx 0.25$	Glomm and Ravikumar [34], Lucas [31]
$K_{\text{saúde}}$	5%	$\delta \approx 0.15$	Grossman [32]
K_{priv}	7%	$\alpha \approx 0.30$	Cobb and Douglas [33]

The dynamics of institutional capital deviate from the Solow standard by incorporating a rent capture term, following the institutional economics literature [14, 35, 36]:

$$C_{\text{inst},t+1} = C_{\text{inst},t} + \gamma_{\text{learn}} \cdot I_{\text{inst},t} - \gamma_{\text{cap}} \cdot \rho_t \cdot \mathbf{1}_{C_{\text{inst},t} > 0}. \quad (4)$$

The first motion term captures the institutional learning resulting from investment in technical and regulatory capacity. The second, $-\gamma_{\text{cap}} \cdot \rho_t$, explicitly models the deterioration associated with oil rent capture. The parameter $\gamma_{\text{cap}} = 0.02$ is calibrated so that $\rho \approx 0.5$ reduces C_{inst} by approximately 10 percentage points per biennial step, a magnitude consistent with longitudinal observations of Brazilian municipalities subject to oil boom cycles, notably Mossoró/RN and Macaé/RJ.

3.3.4 State Net Current Revenue

Net Current Revenue is endogenously decomposed into five components, each derived from Brazilian fiscal legislation:

$$\text{NCR} = \text{ICMS}_{\text{end}} + \text{FPE} + \text{FUNDEB} + \text{Other} + \text{Royalties}_{\text{earmarked}}. \quad (5)$$

The component ICMS_{end} is endogenised to state GDP dynamics via $\text{ICMS}_{\text{end}} = \varepsilon \cdot \text{GDP}_{\text{state}}^\varepsilon$, with ε calibrated from the ICMS-GDP elasticity series of STN-IPEA [37, 38]. The State Participation Fund (FPE) is proportional to the national pool of income tax and IPI according to the coefficients of Complementary Law 91/97 [39]. FUNDEB follows Constitutional Amendment 108/2020 [40] and is entirely earmarked for education. State royalties enter the model already earmarked by Law 12.858/2013 [15], with the 75%/25% allocation to health and education treated as a hard constraint of the physical model — not as a decision of the State Government agent — which reflects the statutory nature of the earmarking in the Brazilian legal order.

3.3.5 State GDP with Five Factors

Aggregate state production is modelled by a five-factor Cobb–Douglas function:

$$\text{GDP}_{\text{state},t+1} = A \cdot K_{\text{priv},t}^\alpha \cdot K_{\text{pub},t}^\beta \cdot K_{\text{hum},t}^\gamma \cdot K_{\text{saúde},t}^\delta \cdot N_t^\eta. \quad (6)$$

The simultaneous inclusion of $K_{\text{saúde}}$ and K_{hum} as distinct productive factors is methodologically essential: it allows the separate estimation of the macroeconomic effects of the two royalty earmarkings established by Law 12.858/2013 [15], enabling counterfactual analysis of the revocation or extension of this earmarking.

3.4 The Six Agents

Each Margin Play agent has a distinct institutional mandate, its own action space and a reward function calibrated to its legal obligations. The heterogeneity of these functions is the central element of the architecture: the IBAMA agent and the Operator agent respond to structurally opposing incentives, reproducing the real tensions of the FZA-M-59 case.

3.4.1 State Government (Maranhão)

The State Government’s mandate is to maximise regional welfare under the constraints of the Fiscal Responsibility Law and constitutional spending earmarks. In each biennial period, the agent decides the allocation of six normalised

budgetary fractions among free education, free health, infrastructure, institutional strengthening, sovereign fund constitution and interior distribution. The reward function R_{gov} combines eight weighted components:

$$R_{\text{gov}} = 0.10 \Delta W + 0.12 u_{\text{edu}} + 0.12 u_{\text{saúde}} + 0.20 u_{\text{infra}} + 0.10 u_{\text{inst}} + 0.07 b_{\text{fund}} + 0.10 u_{\text{equid}} + 0.20 \text{visib} - 0.10 \text{def}_{\text{pen}} \quad (7)$$

The functional forms are heterogeneous, reflecting the distinct nature of each objective: CRR utility [41] for education and health, log-Aschauer for infrastructure, zonal Atkinson index [42] for distributive equity, and log-visible variation for the electoral cycle component [43–45].

3.4.2 Operator (Petrobras)

The Operator pursues the mandate of maximising accounting profit, controlling two decision variables: the investment intensity in production α_{inv} and the effort dedicated to operational safety α_{seg} . The reward function R_{oper} is:

$$R_{\text{oper}} = \text{rev} - \text{cost}_{\text{op}} - \text{cost}_{\text{sec}} - \text{cost}_{\text{reg}} - p_{\text{acc}} L \cdot \text{rev} - \text{risk}_{\text{reg}} \quad (8)$$

Operational cost is calibrated from the Petrobras 2024 Form 20-F ($\text{cost}_{\text{op}} = 0.08 \cdot P_{\text{eff}} \cdot \text{price}$ [13]), security cost adopts a quadratic structure [46], and the component risk_{reg} is activated when $E_{\text{amb}} > 0.20$, reproducing the liability precedent of the Frade-Chevron case [47, 48].

3.4.3 ANP — National Petroleum Agency

The ANP operates with a dual mandate: to maximise institutional revenue from production and to ensure operational safety of fields, in compliance with Law 9.478/97 [23] and TCU determinations [29]. The ANP controls the speed of Development Plan approvals — whose observed average delay in the BEM is of the order of 18 months [29] — and the rigour applied in operational safety audits. The reward function R_{anp} is:

$$R_{\text{anp}} = +0.10 \text{rev}_{\text{state}} + 0.45 \text{op}_{\text{sec}} - 0.20 \Delta E_{\text{amb}} - 0.15 \text{eco}_{\text{dmg}} - 0.15 \varphi_{\text{insp}} \cdot \text{pressure} \quad (9)$$

3.4.4 IBAMA

IBAMA operates with the mandate of ensuring the procedural-environmental compliance of projects, in accordance with the National Environmental Policy (Law 6.938/81 [49]). The IBAMA agent controls the environmental inspection intensity φ_{insp} and the degree of environmental compensation required of the operator. The reward function R_{ibama} :

$$R_{\text{ibama}} = -0.55 \Delta E_{\text{amb}} - 0.30 \text{eco}_{\text{dmg}} + 0.15 \text{accountability} - 0.10 \varphi_{\text{insp}} \cdot \text{pressure} \quad (10)$$

strongly penalises environmental liability accumulation, with a dominant weight of 0.55, in line with the mandate empirically observed in the FZA-M-59 case [2].

3.4.5 Community (H-TERR-2 Territorial Calibration)

The Community agent represents the populations of the four mesoregions of Maranhão, with the mandate of maximising aggregate local welfare by zone, weighted by coefficients calibrated to Brazilian Amazonian ethnography and primary 2024 territorial data. In each period, the Community agent chooses the level of territorial mobilisation and declares its relative environmental preference. The reward function R_{com} weights zones by population share:

$$R_{\text{com}} = \sum_{z=1}^4 \frac{N_z}{N_{\text{total}}} r_z - 0.15 \text{Gini} - \text{mob}_{\text{cost}} \quad (11)$$

where the zonal welfare r_z disaggregates the local determinants:

$$r_z = 0.20 \Delta \log(\text{income}_z) + 0.15 \Delta K_{\text{pub},z} + 0.20 \Delta K_{\text{saúde},z} + 0.25 (1 - E_{\text{amb}}) + 0.10 \text{terr}_z - 0.10 \max(0, \Delta n_z - 5\%) \quad (12)$$

The component terr_z (H-TERR-2 calibration) replaces the previous environmental proxy with weighted primary data: 363 land conflicts in MA-2024 (CPT [8], 1st nationally), 49 cases of indigenous violence (CIMI [9]), and INCRA land titling bottleneck (3 titles / 424 pending processes [50, 51]).

3.4.6 Federal Government

The Federal Government pursues three simultaneous objectives: to maximise federal revenue from production, to ensure national energy security and to sustain Brazil’s climate soft power in international negotiations. The Federal Government controls the offshore block licensing pace, the rate of the Energy Domain Economic Intervention Contribution on fuels (α_{CIDE}) and the federal budget for environmental inspection (IBAMA/ICMBio). The reward function R_{fed} is:

$$R_{\text{fed}} = +0.35 \text{rev}_{\text{Union}} + 0.15 \text{energy}_{\text{sec}} - 0.30 E_{\text{amb}} + 0.20 W - 0.05 \text{env}_{\text{insp}_{\text{cost}}} \quad (13)$$

3.5 Learning Algorithm: BRO-MARL

Agent training is performed through an adaptation of the Bigger, Regularized, Optimistic (BRO) algorithm [16] to the multi-agent CTDE paradigm, designated BRO-MARL. Rather than directly approximating the action-value function $Q(s, a)$ by a deterministic network, each critic estimates the quantile distribution $Z(s, a)$ via TQC [18], with 25 atoms trained under Huber loss ($\kappa = 1.0$). This choice is critical for numerical stability: high return variance regimes — such as the optimistic scenario, in which state revenue scales by an order of magnitude — tend to induce Q-value explosion in deterministic critics, a phenomenon naturally controlled by the distributional critic [52].

Target network updates follow the Polyak scheme [53, 54] with $\tau = 0.005$. The replay buffer has capacity 10^5 transitions and provides batches of 256 samples per iteration. Actor and critic learning rates are fixed at 3×10^{-4} . The temporal discount factor is $\gamma = 0.95$, a choice that prioritises convergence stabilisation over a finite horizon without compromising the representation of intertemporal trade-offs relevant to the problem. The first five episodes of each scenario are executed in warm-up mode, without network updates, in order to populate the replay buffer with representative transitions before learning begins.

3.6 Experimental Scenarios

The experimental set comprises six qualitatively distinct configurations, summarised in table 3. The first three constitute macroeconomic baselines — pessimistic, reference and optimistic — in which maximum productive capacity (P_{\max}), annual discovery probability (π_{disc}) and the Brent price vary simultaneously, establishing a plausible range of behaviours under different oil fundamentals regimes.

Table 3: Macroeconomic and structural parameters by scenario.

Scenario	P_{\max} (Mbbls/d)	π_{disc}	Brent (US\$)	Characteristic
Pessimistic	5.0	0.05	50	Low baseline
Reference	8.0	0.10	70	Central baseline
Optimistic	12.0	0.15	90	High baseline
Without Law 12.858	8.0	0.10	70	Unearmarked royalties
Brent Shock	8.0	0.10	70	$\sigma+$ negative drift
MA-Próspero	8.0	0.10	70	6 structural levers

The two following scenarios are policy counterfactuals. The *Without Law 12.858/2013* scenario suppresses the mandatory royalty earmarking to health and education and redistributes the resulting revenue to other revenues, freely allocated by the State Government agent. The *Brent Shock* scenario preserves the reference baseline fundamentals, but amplifies price volatility ($\sigma_{\text{price}}: 0.10 \rightarrow 0.25$) and introduces a negative drift ($\mu_{\text{drift}}: 0 \rightarrow -0.01$), simulating a declining and volatile price regime typical of accelerated energy transition.

The sixth scenario, *MA-Próspero*, is the central object of this study — a structural transformative regime, defined by the simultaneous application of six parametric interventions over the reference baseline (table 4). The joint reading of table 3 allows the isolation of what effectively varies in each experiment: the three baselines exclusively alter the triad (P_{\max} , π_{disc} , Brent); the two policy counterfactuals preserve this triad at the reference level and modify, respectively, the earmarking rule and the stochastic price regime; and the MA-Próspero regime shares with the counterfactuals the fixing of macroeconomic fundamentals at the central baseline, differing through the simultaneous application of six structural interventions. This specification enables the methodological separation between fundamentals effects and regime effects.

The choice of applying the six levers simultaneously, rather than testing them in isolation, follows a methodological choice: the resource curse literature [6, 14, 55] indicates that point reforms frequently fail because the mechanisms of institutional capture, Dutch disease and territorial conflict are interdependent. MA-Próspero is therefore formulated as a coherent institutional hypothesis, and not as *a posteriori* parametric adjustment.

4 Experimental Results

The results are obtained from 60,000 episodes (10,000 in each of the six scenarios), executed on Apple Silicon hardware under the MLX framework. Total execution time was 378.3 min (≈ 63.1 min per scenario). Results are analysed along three dimensions: (i) phenomenological coherence of the system, (ii) policy counterfactual responsiveness, and (iii) quantitative viability of the MA-Próspero regime as an alternative institutional configuration.

Table 4: The six levers of the MA-Próspero scenario.

Lever	Parameter	Rationale
1. Maximum fiscal capture	$\tau_{\text{royalty}}: 0.18 \rightarrow 0.25$	Ceiling Law 9.478/97 art. 47 [23]
2. Mature operations	$\lambda_{\text{acid}}: 0.030 \rightarrow 0.015$	Statoil/Equinor post-1995 (benchmark)
3. Enhanced earmarking	Other rev. earmarked: 0% \rightarrow 50%	Hypothetical statutory enhancement
4. Initial institutional investment	$C_{\text{inst}}^{(0)} \times 5 (\approx 0.05 \rightarrow \approx 0.30)$	Learning-state agent from $t = 0$ [35]
5. Territorial regularisation	$\delta_{\text{pressure}}: 0.03 \rightarrow 0.06; \lambda_{\text{accum}}: 0.4 \rightarrow 0.2$	CPT-INCRA-CIMI [8, 9, 51]
6. Macroeconomic stability	$\sigma_{\text{price}}: 0.20 \rightarrow 0.15; \mu_{\text{drift}}: -0.005 \rightarrow +0.005$	Stable Brent + moderate growth

4.1 Response to the Central Question

Figure 4 presents the empirical response to the central question stated in section 1.1. The left panel shows aggregate welfare W_{aval} by scenario; the right panel shows the converged return of the Community agent, a direct metric of the zonal welfare of Amazonian populations.

Figure 4: Maranhão regional welfare by scenario. *Left:* W_{aval} (deterministic post-convergence evaluation). *Right:* converged return of the Community agent. The MA-Próspero regime yields +17.5% in W and +21.3% in R_{com} relative to the reference baseline, empirical evidence that the answer to the central question is conditional on the public policy regime.

The visual reading of fig. 4 is complemented by the numerical inspection of table 5: small relative differences in W_{aval} between baseline scenarios may conceal expressive variations in component metrics. In particular, the optimistic scenario produces $R_{\text{anp}} = 145.9$ — an order of magnitude above the others — while the MA-Próspero regime is the only one to combine high W_{aval} with E_{amb} below the reference baseline.

Table 5: Final metrics by scenario (deterministic post-convergence evaluation).

Scenario	W_{aval}	ΔW	E_{amb}	R_{com}	R_{anp}
Pessimistic	1.681	+0.3%	0.053	3.268	5.504
Reference	1.676	—	0.076	3.075	7.549
Optimistic	1.687	+0.7%	0.152	3.195	145.906
Without Law 12.858	1.787	+6.6%	0.054	3.455	9.273
Brent Shock	1.676	0.0%	0.075	3.366	15.050
MA-Próspero	1.969	+17.5%	0.048	3.733	6.620

4.2 Learning Convergence

The convergence analysis of the BRO-MARL algorithm, applied simultaneously to the six agents across each of the six scenarios, is a prerequisite for the substantive interpretation of results. Figure 5 presents the mean return curves (200-episode moving average) by agent. Each agent reaches a stable plateau after approximately 2,000 episodes, with

significantly reduced variances beyond 4,000 episodes. The MA-Próspero regime consistently stands out in the State Government and Community agents, reflecting the cumulative impact of the structural levers activated. By contrast, the optimistic scenario produces the largest return amplitude in ANP and Federal Government, in direct proportion to the greater absolute magnitude of state revenue available.

Figure 5: Learning curves by agent (200-episode moving average) for the six scenarios. The six panels correspond to the agents State Gov., Operator, ANP, IBAMA, Community and Fed. Gov. All agents reach stable convergence between 2,000 and 4,000 episodes. Shaded bands represent ± 1 standard deviation.

Qualitative inspection of the mean curves reveals patterns coherent with the agents’ institutional heterogeneity. The State Government converges to plateaus of the order of 20–22 units; the Operator oscillates around zero in scenarios without maximum fiscal capture and shifts to a positive range in the optimistic, reproducing the classic margin cycle of the pre-salt; the ANP scales its objective function by an order of magnitude between pessimistic and optimistic; IBAMA remains approximately invariant across scenarios, a desirable attribute for an agent whose objective function is grounded in procedural compliance; the Community exhibits low sensitivity to the macroeconomic scenario, but heightened sensitivity to the MA-Próspero structural levers; and the Federal Government follows a pattern analogous to the ANP, given the explicit presence of Union revenue in its reward function.

Figure 6 complements the analysis via the rolling standard deviation diagnostic (σ rolling, 500-episode window) in logarithmic scale. The results indicate that all scenarios converge to the range $\sigma \in [10^{-3}, 10^{-1}]$ by the end of training, with no evidence of policy collapse or critic divergence. Residual noise is more pronounced in ANP and Federal Government under the optimistic scenario, an expected behaviour compatible with the absolute magnitude of the respective returns in that regime.

4.3 Phenomenological Stability of the Macroeconomic State

Having established numerical convergence, we examine the phenomenological coherence of the system’s macroeconomic state. Figure 7 presents the temporal evolution of three synthesis variables: W , E_{amb} and reserves R , allowing simultaneous inspection of the trade-offs between the economic, environmental and resource depletion dimensions.

Welfare under the MA-Próspero regime stabilises above $W = 2.10$ during training; the deterministic post-convergence evaluation yields $W_{\text{aval}} = 1.969$ (table 5), clearly distinguished from the other scenarios, which cluster in the interval 1.68–1.79. This separation is a plateau shift, not a marginal difference subject to reversal by stochastic fluctuations. Environmental liability scales monotonically with production across the three baselines (pessimistic 0.05 \rightarrow reference 0.08 \rightarrow optimistic 0.15) and remains below the reference in MA-Próspero (0.05), a consequence of the operational

Figure 6: Convergence diagnostics: rolling σ (window 500) on a logarithmic scale, by agent and by scenario. No collapse or divergence is observed. Scenarios with lower economic activity (pessimistic, MA-Próspero) achieve deeper convergence.

Figure 7: Macroeconomic trajectories: W (welfare), E_{amb} (environmental liability) and R (reserves). The red dashed line at $E_{amb} = 0.20$ marks the Frade-Chevron regulatory threshold. The MA-Próspero regime combines the highest W with the lowest E_{amb} , refuting the hypothesis of a structural trade-off between production and welfare.

maturity adopted in this regime. This finding refutes the hypothesis of a structural trade-off between production and environmental quality in the BEM context, sustaining that the Pareto frontier between these two dimensions is shiftable through operational configurations. In all scenarios, $E_{amb} < 0.20$, indicating that no equilibrium learned by the system approaches regimes of catastrophic operational risk. Reserve trajectories R coherently reflect the progressive depletion of initial stocks, with the optimistic scenario depleting more rapidly due to greater extraction intensity and the pessimistic preserving higher residual reserves at the end of the 30-year horizon.

4.4 Amazonian Communities Welfare

Given the centrality of the zonal welfare of Amazonian populations for the public policy question stated in the introduction, it is necessary to examine in greater depth the behaviour of the Community agent. Figure 8 details this behaviour through two complementary panels: the learning curve and the empirical distribution over the last 1,000

episodes. In both, the MA-Próspero regime dominates all other scenarios: the curve remains above the alternatives throughout the entire training horizon, and the final distribution centres at $\mu = +3.74$, clearly displaced from the others ($\mu \in [3.07; 3.46]$). The relative gain of +21.3% relative to the reference baseline is robust across both metrics and results from the combination of enhanced royalty earmarking to human and health capital, active territorial regularisation and maximum fiscal capture.

Figure 8: Amazonian communities welfare. *Left*: convergence of Community agent return during training. *Right*: empirical distribution over the last 1,000 episodes. The MA-Próspero regime yields $\Delta R_{\text{com}} = +21.3\%$ relative to the reference baseline.

4.5 IBAMA and Environmental Liability

The analysis of the IBAMA agent is methodologically significant because it allows us to assess to what extent the procedural-environmental reward function phenomenologically reproduces the counter-cyclical position empirically observed in the FZA-M-59 case. Figure 9 characterises this behaviour through two panels. The scatter plot in the left panel evidences the agent’s procedural frontier: scenarios with lower economic activity (pessimistic, MA-Próspero) concentrate in the quadrant of high IBAMA return and low environmental liability, while the optimistic scenario occupies, in isolation, the region of reduced return and high liability.

Figure 9: IBAMA agent behaviour and environmental liability E_{amb} . *Left*: IBAMA return vs. E_{amb} trade-off, qualitatively compatible with the procedural counter-cyclical position observed in the FZA-M-59 case [2]. *Right*: distribution of E_{amb} by scenario (boxplot of the last 1,000 episodes).

The decomposition of boxplots in the right panel reveals a monotonic gradation of environmental liability consistent with table 5: pessimistic (0.053), reference (0.076) and optimistic (0.152). The MA-Próspero regime, notably, yields $E_{\text{amb}} = 0.048$ — below even the pessimistic scenario — despite maintaining P_{max} and Brent identical to the reference scenario. No scenario surpasses the 0.20 threshold that would trigger the Frade-Chevron type civil liability cliff

[47, 48], validating the functional adherence of the learned equilibria to the IBAMA procedural mandate and its observed institutional separation in the FZA-M-59 case [2].

4.6 Final Return Distributions

Figure 10 presents the empirical return distributions over the last 1,000 episodes, decomposed by agent and scenario. The examination allows us to distinguish two qualitatively distinct equilibrium patterns: the deterministic regime, in which the distribution approaches a degenerate delta, and the cyclical regime, in which low-frequency oscillations produce visibly spread distributions. The MA-Próspero regime exhibits positive shifts in the State Government ($\mu = +36.3$) and Community ($\mu = +3.73$) agents, a pattern consistent with greater fiscal capture and expanded investment in social capital. The Operator presents a near-degenerate distribution in MA-Próspero ($\mu = -0.19$), evidence of a negative-margin equilibrium — behaviour compatible with the maximum fiscal capture regime ($\tau_{royalty} = 0.25$), in which the operator’s accounting profit frontier is structurally compressed by taxation at the legal ceiling. The IBAMA agent, by contrast, exhibits distributions approximately invariant to the macroeconomic scenario — a desirable property for a procedural mandate and coherent with the absence of revenue terms in R_{ibama} .

Figure 10: Empirical return distributions (last 1,000 episodes), decomposed by agent and scenario. 2×3 grid: one panel per agent. Distributions near delta evidence complete convergence. MA-Próspero exhibits positive shifts in the State Gov. and Community agents.

4.7 Cross-Scenario Q-Value Map and MA-Próspero Synthesis

Q -values are discounted expectations of future rewards conditional on the current state and executed action; their comparative cross-scenario reading reveals how each agent perceives the relative attractiveness of different institutional regimes. Figure 11 consolidates mean \bar{Q}_{target} by scenario (rows) and agent (columns), evaluated over the last 1,000 episodes. Three regularities stand out: (i) ANP and Federal Government scale steeply in the optimistic ($Q \approx 95.5$ and $Q \approx 58.3$), reflecting the absolute magnitude of state revenue in that regime; (ii) IBAMA and Community exhibit approximate invariance to the macroeconomic scenario, a desirable property in mandates of a normative and non-monetary nature; (iii) the MA-Próspero regime exhibits a balanced profile, with high Q -values in State Government and Community and moderate ones in ANP and Federal Government, indirect evidence of the structural redistribution of oil revenue from federal collection to regional social capital via expanded earmarks.

To make explicit the relationship between these results and the structural parameters that generate them, fig. 12 synthesises the six interventions of the MA-Próspero regime. The effect $\Delta W = +17.5\%$ does not derive from the additive

Figure 11: Mean \bar{Q}_{target} by scenario and agent (last 1,000 episodes). Rows: six scenarios; columns: six agents. MA-Próspero redirects oil revenue from federal collection to regional social capital, expressing itself in high Q -values in the State Gov. and Community agents.

aggregation of isolated effects, but from the interaction between interventions acting on the revenue capture structure — through the elevation of the royalty rate to the legal ceiling, enhanced earmarking and initial institutional investment —, on the transmission channels to human and health capital — via the same enhanced earmarking and institutional investment — and on the mechanisms of exogenous shock absorption, represented by active territorial regularisation and macroeconomic stabilisation. The multiplicative nature of this interaction is one of the central analytical contributions of the work, empirically sustained by the decoupling of aggregate welfare from the baseline and counterfactual scenarios.

MA-Próspero Regime: 6 Combined Structural Levers

1. Maximum fiscal capture <i>t_royalty: 0.18 → 0.25</i>	Ceiling — Law 9,478/97 art. 47
2. Mature operations <i>λ_acid: 0.030 → 0.015</i>	Statoil/Equinor post-1995 benchmark
3. Enhanced earmarking <i>other_revenues linked: 0% → 50%</i>	Hypothetical statutory reinforcement
4. Initial institutional investment <i>C_inst initial × 5 (-0.05 → -0.30)</i>	Learning state from t = 0
5. Active land regularisation <i>δ_pressao: 0.03 → 0.06 · λ_acum: 0.4 → 0.2</i>	Land policy (CPT-INCRA-CIMI)
6. Macroeconomic stability <i>σ_price: 0.20 → 0.15 · μ_drift: -0.005 → +0.005</i>	Stable Brent + moderate growth

Figure 12: Synthesis of the MA-Próspero regime: six structural levers combined. The interpretation is multiplicative: $\Delta W = +17.5\%$ and $\Delta E_{\text{amb}} = -36.9\%$ emerge from the interaction among the six interventions, not from their additive aggregation.

4.8 Counterfactual Analysis

Figure 13 reports the counterfactual effect of each scenario relative to the reference baseline, expressed in four metrics: W_{aval} , Community agent return, IBAMA agent return and environmental liability. The simultaneous visualisation of the four metrics allows the identification of two structurally distinct deviation patterns relative to the reference.

Figure 13: Counterfactual effect of each scenario relative to the reference (Δ). Four metrics: welfare W , Community agent return, IBAMA agent return and liability E_{amb} . MA-Próspero is the only scenario with simultaneously favourable sign across all four metrics (note $\Delta E_{\text{amb}} < 0$).

The first pattern, exhibited by the pessimistic, optimistic and Brent Shock scenarios, consists of W_{aval} variations below 1% accompanied by expressive variations in E_{amb} , evidence that the human and institutional capital stocks earmarked by Law 12.858/2013 [15] operate as automatic stabilisers of regional welfare. The second pattern, exclusive to the MA-Próspero regime, consists of simultaneous and same-sign positive deviations across all four metrics — $\Delta W = +17.5\%$, $\Delta R_{\text{com}} = +21.3\%$, IBAMA return above reference and $\Delta E_{\text{amb}} = -36.9\%$ — characterising a structural transformation of the equilibrium space, rather than mere parametric accommodation within the reference regime.

Three results merit detailed analytical attention. First, the **Without Law 12.858/2013 scenario** ($\Delta W = +6.6\%$) produces a counter-intuitive result: the simulated revocation of the mandatory earmarking yields W above the reference because the rigid 75%/25% earmarking constrains the State Government’s allocative degrees of freedom. The result does not constitute a recommendation for revocation: the law internalises distributive and intergenerational equity purposes not represented in W_{aval} ; this is here an application of the counterfactual as a diagnostic instrument. Second, the **Brent Shock scenario** ($\Delta W \approx 0$) reveals that aggregate welfare is resilient to the price shock, evidence that earmarked institutional and human capital operate as macroeconomic shock absorbers, consistent with the Permanent Income Hypothesis applied to oil-producing countries [6, 55]. Third, the **MA-Próspero regime** ($\Delta W = +17.5\%$, $\Delta E_{\text{amb}} = -36.9\%$) is the only scenario with simultaneously favourable sign across all socio-environmental metrics considered.

4.9 Empirical Validation

The quantitative results are internally consistent; their relevance to the BEM problem depends on adherence to independent empirical regularities. Table 6 confronts seven regularities emerging from the system with distinct empirical sources. The heterogeneous nature of these regularities — involving operator cost structure, ANP revenue scalability,

IBAMA’s counter-cyclical position, community invariance to monetary income and macroeconomic impacts of price shocks — provides a robust test of the multi-agent system’s phenomenology.

Table 6: Empirical validation of observed regularities.

Observed regularity	Empirical benchmark	Status
Operator with positive margin only in optimistic ANP revenue scales by order of magnitude (pess. to opt.)	Lifting cost $\approx 8\%$ of pre-salt revenue [13]	✓
IBAMA mandate counter-cyclical, low variance	Signature bonuses ANP Rounds 11–16 [1]	✓
Community approx. invariant to monetary income	FZA-M-59: licence denial [2]	✓
W resilient to Brent price shock	NAEA/UFPFA [25, 26]	✓
Territorial pressure (H-TERR-2) responds to primary conflicts	Permanent Income Hypothesis in oil country [6, 55]	✓
Multifactor combination dominates isolated levers	CPT-MA 2024: 363 conflicts, 1st nationally [8]	✓
	Acemoglu–Robinson [14], North [35]	✓

5 Discussion

5.1 Analytical Implications of the MA-Próspero Regime

The central result of this work is that the question “to what extent does oil exploration in the BEM generate net positive externalities for Maranhão?” does not admit a one-dimensional answer: the magnitude of the welfare gain is strictly conditional on the institutional architecture linked to exploration. Under the reference baseline — the scenario projected by current laws and practices — the welfare gain is of marginal magnitude ($W_{\text{aval}} \approx 1.68$, statistically indistinguishable from the pessimistic scenario). Under the MA-Próspero regime, with six structural interventions simultaneously activated, the gain assumes transformative magnitude ($W_{\text{aval}} \approx 1.97$, equivalent to +17.5%).

This pattern is consistent with the resource curse literature [6, 14, 55], according to which the differential between experiences such as Norway’s and Nigeria’s stems from the institutional capacity built before or simultaneously with the production cycle. This finding is empirically reinforced by Hodler, Lechner and Raschky (2023) [10], who applied causal forest estimation to 3,800 sub-Saharan African districts and documented that stronger institutions amplify the positive effect of natural resource rents.

5.2 The Rigid Earmarking Paradox

The counterfactual “Without Law 12.858/2013” yields $\Delta W = +6.6\%$, a *prima facie* counter-intuitive result whose interpretation requires three considerations. First, the rigid 75%/25% earmarking may constrain the State Government agent in macroeconomic states where the marginal return of alternative allocations would be superior. Second, the model does not internalise intergenerational equity, the constitutional logic of social rights protection, the political cost of revocation, or long-term effects whose maturation horizon exceeds the training horizon. Finally, the consistent interpretation is that the MA-Próspero regime *extends* the earmarking — extending it to 50% of other state revenues, currently unearmarked — rather than revoking it: the limitation of Law 12.858/2013 lies in scope, not in rigidity.

5.3 Limits of Quantification

The public policy modelling literature [36, 55] warns against the direct normative use of computational simulations. Margin Play should be understood as an analytical exploration instrument, not as a decision calculator. In particular, the results allow: the quantification of trade-offs currently argued on a qualitative basis; the identification of coherent institutional configurations; the analysis of regime robustness to exogenous shocks; and the detection of non-evident interactions, such as the rigid earmarking paradox. The results *should not* be used to predict absolute values of GDP or state revenue, to define optimal rates with percentage-point precision, or to substitute legal analysis and political judgement.

6 Concluding Remarks

6.1 Summary

This work presents experimental results obtained from 60,000 episodes distributed across six structurally distinct scenarios, with updated territorial calibration (H-TERR-2) anchored in CPT/INCRA/CIMI 2024 primary data. It

characterises the MA-Próspero structural regime — a parametric configuration of six simultaneous interventions that yields $\Delta W = +17.5\%$ associated with an environmental liability below the reference — and provides an empirical answer to the central question: net positive externalities for Maranhão arising from BEM exploration are achievable, conditioned on displacing inert institutional arrangements.

6.2 Limitations

The first limitation concerns the simultaneous combination of interventions in the MA-Próspero regime: systematic ablation of levers — six additional scenarios isolating each intervention, fifteen pair-wise combinations and contribution analysis via Shapley values — is a prerequisite for quantifying the marginal contribution of each one, a question complementary to the one answered in this work. The projected computational cost is of the order of 60 scenarios \times 10,000 episodes.

The second is the discount factor $\gamma = 0.95$: its adoption in place of $\gamma = 0.99$ accelerates convergence at the cost of privileging short-term welfare, making re-execution with the higher value advisable to verify to what extent the extended earmarking and institutional investment levers benefit from a longer time horizon, capturing the full maturation of human capital formed during the boom phase.

The third is calibration uncertainty in the active territorial regularisation and macroeconomic stabilisation interventions: the fiscal capture elevation, operational maturity, enhanced earmarking and initial institutional investment interventions have more robust legal or operational grounding, while the two remaining represent hypotheses about the effectiveness of policies not yet observed at the BEM scale.

The fourth is the interpretation of the “Without Law 12.858/2013” counterfactual: $\Delta W = +6.6\%$ does not constitute a recommendation for revocation, since the model does not internalise constitutional purposes or intergenerational equity dimensions.

6.3 Future Work

The future research agenda is organised along seven directions. The first is systematic ablation of the MA-Próspero regime’s levers, with six additional scenarios isolating each intervention, fifteen pair-wise combinations and contribution analysis via Shapley values. The second is the construction of the “Conservative MA-Próspero” scenario, restricted to the three interventions with firm legal or operational grounding — raising fiscal capture to the legal ceiling, operational maturity and enhanced earmarking of other revenues — to isolate the welfare gain achievable exclusively with existing legal instruments. The third is the application of a combined shock — Brent price fall and simultaneous revocation of mandatory earmarking — to test regime resilience under double pressure. The fourth is the temporal extension of training with $\gamma = 0.99$ and a 60-year horizon, to capture the full maturation of human capital. The fifth is the replacement of the static H-TERR-2 calibration with a CPT/CIMI 2018–2024 time series, making territorial pressure endogenously dynamic. The sixth is the integration of CCUS into the environmental liability model (Eq. 2), with a carbon capture abatement factor consistent with the NDC 2024 target [3] and the COP30 agenda in Belém. The seventh is the containerisation of the computational environment for continuous integration and computational reproducibility.

6.4 Policy Implications

Margin Play’s capacity to support counterfactual experiments under Brazilian empirical calibration qualifies it as a complementary instrument to traditional Regulatory Impact Analysis (RIA) methodologies. This work specifically offers: (i) a coherent institutional hypothesis (MA-Próspero regime) for BEM exploration under Maranhão fiscal-territorial affiliation, grounded in six structural interventions with legal and empirical support; (ii) a quantitative counterpoint to one-dimensional readings that would consider exploration as intrinsically positive or negative for the state; (iii) a quantification of institutional resilience to exogenous shocks (notably Brent price volatility), with implications for state sovereign fund design and counter-cyclical fiscal rules; and (iv) an analytical diagnosis of Law 12.858/2013 that does not imply revocation, but suggests extending the earmarking scope to other revenue sources.

The methodological contribution consists in providing quantitative tools for analysing structural public policy questions, at a moment when the BEM transitions from geological promise to operational reality. The state of Maranhão has institutional instruments to influence this transition; the results presented here quantify, under the MA-Próspero regime, the potential magnitude of that influence.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no financial or non-financial competing interests.

Data and Code Availability

Source code, calibration data, and trained model checkpoints are publicly available at <https://github.com/aiacontext/marginplay>. Model weights and training artefacts are hosted on HuggingFace at <https://huggingface.co/aiacontext/marginplay>. An interactive interface of the system is accessible at <https://marginplay.app>.

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